

Minutes EB23-04
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
7 August 2023 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barney Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Apology

Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Upcoming conferences: BISMIS and TDWG (see below)

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

Action items from previous meeting

1. *IS and FV to investigate archiving the minutes on Zenodo.*

Community named "SeqCode Matters" was created at zenodo.com to store public SeqCode documents. All documents will receive a DOI.

2. *MC and FV to alert the broader community of the posting of the minutes via email, twitter and slack.*

Alerts posted via twitter. An email with the most recent information will be sent to the SeqCode community once the minutes of this meeting has been finalized. MC to ask ISME office to replace the current link to the repository for the minutes on the website with the Zenodo link.

3. *LMR to investigate hosting of rocket.chat on Innsbruck server.*

Program to run rocket.chat has been installed. System will be tested in the near future.

4. *LMR to provide a proposal on how best to spend the ISME funding for the development of the Registry. LMR to develop a brief to communicate the funding for a prize (grant) to the person or group with the best proposal to further develop the registry.*

A prize similar to the ASM Microbiome Data Prize will be created. The prize will cover the recipient's attendance to ISME19. LMR to prepare the final description for sharing within the SeqCode community. The target date for the awarding of the prize will be Feb 2024.

5. *MC to prepare a letter to the Editors of relevant journals on how they can obtain relevant information related to the registration of names prior to publication.*

Only a short paragraph with instructions to authors will be provided to the journals. It will contain the links to the SeqCode registry and contact form. The detailed description of the registration procedure which will be hosted at the Registry website is envisioned to be added shortly.

6. *KK, BW and ALR to meet with Brian Hedlund and Alison Murray to follow-up on the NFS' RCN and ICB funding on 10 April.*

Stand over. KK will initiate this discussion amongst US members

7. BW and ALR will write a piece for ASM's *Microcosm* newsletter.

BW wrote a blog with Brian Hedlund which was posted on the ASM website

(<https://asm.org/Articles/2023/July/SeqCode-Provides-a-Path-to-Name-Uncultivated-Proka>)

Ongoing action items

1. EB to prepare a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode for submission to ISME communications after January 2024.

2. LMR to investigate the EU COST Action funding.

To have a viable proposal a team based on the funding requirements will have to be brought together. Suggestion of partners, especially groups from COST Inclusiveness Target Countries (e.g East European and some of the Mediterranean countries) should be shared with LMR.

3. FW to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

4. BW to submit amendments of SeqCode regarding *Candidatus* and orthography.

Proposal has been submitted to ISME Communications.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

This commission will have its first meeting when proposals to amend the SeqCode are received. It is expected that the first meeting will be held during the second half of the year.

Standards Working Group

The working group is requested to discuss the impact of polyploidy on the current quality criteria related to contamination. The issue of genomes with a large number of contigs has also been raised. PH will provide KK with an update on the meeting of the Genomic Standards Consortium.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

The new intern is providing valuable assistance. Issues related to the operation and improvement of the registry are shared via GitHub. In future, there will be an opportunity for a post doc interested in taxonomy or bioinformatics to work with LMR or in partnership with Maria Dzunkova (coopted member of RNWG) from the University of Valencia. The NMDC may provide some in kind support to the Registry.

Reconciliation Commission

The proposal for the possible validation of a name linked to a poor-quality genome to ensure the stability of the names of the higher-ranking taxa linked to its genus is still open on GitHub until September.

5. Amendments of SeqCode

Changes to the SeqCode related to arbitrary names and the naming of taxa above the phylum level should be investigated and discussed in greater detail to decide if changes to the code should be suggested.

6. SeqCode logo

After some discussion the following logo was approved:

7. Vocabulary changes in the registry

The proposal by LMR to change the term “Approved” to “Endorsed” when reporting on the status of proposed names in the Registry, was excepted by the EB.

8. Application for ISME19 activities

The EB was informed that KK, LMR and FV plan to propose a workshop focusing on the bioinformatic analysis and naming of MAGs. MC suggested to include name formation and registration during this workshop if possible. The EB also support the proposal by MC to apply for a round table discussion at the conference.

9. Updates

KK and FV reported that the planning for the special SeqCode issue of Systematic and Applied Microbiology (SAM) is progressing well.

MC and PH suggested that a manuscript assessing the progress made with the SeqCode should be prepared early in 2024. A link to an outline of the paper was shared with the EB members as well as members of the former SeqCode Steering Committee. It was suggested that it should be timed to follow after publication of the special SeqCode issue of SAM. The target audience should be microbial ecologists.

The meeting was adjourned.

New action items

1. FV to send out a poll to determine the date of the next meeting.
2. FV to circulate the minutes to the EB for their comments within a set time period.
3. MC to arrange for the posting of the minutes on the ISME webpage via Zenodo repository.
4. FV to share the EB minutes and other relevant information with the SeqCode Community via email.
5. LMR to finalize and share a brief communication on the proposed prize.
6. MC to share the instruction to authors with the relevant journals.
7. KK to investigate possible RCN funding
8. EB members should provide LMR with the details of possible contacts in COST Inclusiveness Target Countries.
9. MC to prepare a proposal for a round table discussion at ISME19.

Ongoing action items

1. EB to prepare a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode for submission to ISME communications after January 2024.
2. FW to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

Minutes prepared by FV, Aug 7, 2023

Approved Aug 15, 2023